

Weekly Progress Report

Date: 09/11/2015 – 13/11/2015

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Plans:

- Discussion of firmware architecture of RS mote to be included in the design proposal
- Begin and conclude work on Revision 4 of Evaluation Report
- Continue to work on PhD Proposal documents

Activities:

- A first version of the firmware architecture was agreed upon and is contained in Revision 4 of the Bergen prototype evaluation report.
- A deadline for the conclusion of incorporating the feedback from Revision 3 of the said report was set for Tuesday 17 November.

Plans for next week

- Submit Revision 4 in time
- Make arrangements for starting work on the open source Contiki firmware. Mary to initiate contact with her department in search of able students.